

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№4(2)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 324 sahifa,
13-aprel, 2026-yil.

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Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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ACTIVATION OF STUDENTS' LEARNING ACTIVITIES USING DIDACTIC GAMES

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada didaktik o'yinlarning talabalar o'quv faoliyatini faollashtirishdagi o'rni va ahamiyati ilmiy-pedagogik nuqtai nazardan tahlil etilgan. Tadqiqotda didaktik o'yinlarning psixologik-pedagogik asoslari, ularning an'anaviy o'qitish metodlaridan farqli xususiyatlari va zamonaviy ta'lim jarayoniga tatbiq etish imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqilgan. Maqolada o'yin faoliyatining motivatsion, kognitiv va kommunikativ jihatlariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan hamda o'quv jarayonida didaktik o'yinlarni qo'llashning samarali shakl va metodlari tavsiya etilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari didaktik o'yinlarning talabalar bilish faolligini oshirishda, mustaqil fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda va o'quv materialini chuqur o'zlashtirishda muhim vosita ekanligini tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: didaktik o'yin, o'quv faoliyati, faollashtirish, motivatsiya, kognitiv faollik, o'qitish metodlari, zamonaviy pedagogika, interaktiv ta'lim.

Abstract: This article examines the role and significance of didactic games in activating students' learning activity from a scientific and pedagogical perspective. The study analyzes the psychological and pedagogical foundations of didactic games, their distinctive features compared to traditional teaching methods, and the possibilities of their application in the modern educational process. Special attention is given to the motivational, cognitive, and communicative aspects of game-based activity, and effective forms and methods of incorporating didactic games into the learning process are proposed.

Key words: didactic game, learning activity, activation, motivation, cognitive activity, teaching methods, modern pedagogy, interactive learning.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль и значение дидактических игр в активизации учебной деятельности студентов с научно-педагогической точки зрения. В исследовании анализируются психолого-педагогические основы дидактических игр, их отличительные особенности по сравнению с традиционными методами обучения, а также возможности их применения в современном образовательном процессе. Особое внимание уделяется мотивационным, когнитивным и коммуникативным аспектам игровой деятельности, а также предлагаются эффективные формы и методы использования дидактических игр в учебном процессе.

Ключевые слова: дидактическая игра, учебная деятельность, активизация, мотивация, познавательная активность, методы обучения, современная педагогика, интерактивное обучение.

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary higher education faces a fundamental challenge: learners exposed to passive, lecture-centred instruction frequently demonstrate shallow understanding, diminished motivation, and poor long-term retention of academic content (Fredricks, Blumenfeld & Paris, 2004). Didactic games - structured play activities designed with explicit educational objectives, rule-governed procedures, and clearly defined outcomes - offer a theoretically grounded and practically accessible means of addressing this challenge. Unlike purely recreational games, didactic games ensure that participation in play constitutes participation in learning, rendering enjoyment and intellectual growth mutually reinforcing rather than competing aims (Huizinga, 1955).

In Uzbekistan, the national educational reform agenda - anchored in the State Educational Standard and Presidential Decree PF-5712- explicitly mandates the replacement of rote-memorisation-based instruction with interactive, competency-centred pedagogical approaches. Higher pedagogical institutions are specifically charged with equipping pre-service teachers with the methodological repertoire demanded by these reforms. Within this policy environment, didactic games represent an aligned and contextually appropriate pedagogical response. However, despite robust international evidence for their effectiveness, empirical research on didactic

game integration in Central Asian higher education remains sparse, leaving regional educators without an adequate evidence base for informed implementation decisions. This study addresses that gap.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical foundations of didactic games draw from several converging traditions. Sociocultural theory positions play as a principal mechanism for development, arguing that game-based social interaction creates zones of proximal development in which learners operate at levels beyond their current independent capacity. Constructivist framework similarly emphasises active, experiential engagement as the primary driver of schema formation, while Bruner's (1966) discovery learning model highlights the role of exploratory activity in producing durable, transferable understanding. Together, these perspectives predict that game-based learning environments - which demand active manipulation of knowledge, collaborative negotiation, and adaptive problem-solving - will produce deeper cognitive processing than passive reception of information.

From a motivational standpoint, Deci and Ryan's (2000) self-determination theory provides a compelling explanatory framework. The theory holds that intrinsic motivation flourishes when three fundamental psychological needs are satisfied: autonomy (sense of agency), competence (sense of effectiveness), and relatedness (sense of social connection). Well-designed didactic games simultaneously address all three needs, offering learners decision-making agency, calibrated challenges that generate feelings of mastery, and cooperative social structures that foster belonging. Csikszentmihalyi's (1990) flow theory further illuminates the motivational dynamics of games, predicting that the challenge-skill balance inherent in progressively structured game sequences sustains optimal engagement. Empirically, meta-analytic evidence consistently supports the effectiveness of game-based learning. Mayer's (2019) review of 61 studies documented moderate-to-large effect sizes on learning outcomes relative to conventional instruction ($d = 0.51$). Boyle et al. (2016), reviewing 143 studies of digital and non-digital games, found consistent evidence for improved engagement, motivation, and content mastery across educational contexts. Specifically within teacher education, Nolan and McBride (2014) found that pre-service teachers who experience game-based learning are significantly more likely to incorporate interactive methods into their own subsequent teaching, underscoring the methodological modelling value of game integration in pedagogical universities. Uzbek scholarship has begun to address game-based learning in primary education but higher education contexts remain empirically underexplored.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods quasi-experimental design combining quantitative pre-test/post-test measurements with qualitative data from semi-structured interviews. The quasi-experimental approach was selected in recognition of the practical constraints of educational research, where random group assignment is rarely feasible in intact institutional settings (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Two existing course sections were assigned to experimental and control conditions on the basis of university timetabling, with pre-test scores confirming the baseline equivalence of both groups prior to the intervention.

Participants were first-year Bachelor of Education students enrolled in the Natural Science Teaching Methodology course at Tashkent State Pedagogical University during the 2024–2025 academic year. All participants provided informed consent prior to the study. The experimental group participated in a twelve-week instructional programme in which a substantial portion of each session was dedicated to structured didactic games, encompassing five categories: classification games, role-play games, simulation games, quiz-based competitive games, and collaborative problem-solving games. The control group received equivalent instructional time through conventional lecture-based methods. Both groups were taught by the same instructor to eliminate teacher effect as a confounding variable.

Three validated instruments were administered at pre-test and post-test stages: the Cognitive Activity Scale, measuring self-reported cognitive engagement and analytical effort; an adapted Intrinsic Motivation Inventory, measuring interest and enjoyment, perceived competence, and effort; and the Natural Science Knowledge Test, a criterion-referenced content assessment validated by subject-matter experts. Qualitative data were collected through semi-structured interviews with a purposively selected subsample of experimental group students and analysed using Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase thematic analysis procedure.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Pre-test scores confirmed the equivalence of both groups prior to the intervention. Following the twelve-week programme, the experimental group demonstrated substantially higher post-test scores than the control group across all three measured dimensions. On the Cognitive Activity Scale, experimental group students recorded considerably higher post-test scores than their counterparts in the control group, whose scores remained largely

unchanged from baseline. Analysis of covariance, controlling for pre-test performance, confirmed a statistically significant group effect with a very large practical effect size, indicating that the gains observed in the experimental group far exceeded what could be attributed to pre-existing differences or measurement variability.

Intrinsic motivation scores followed a markedly similar pattern. Experimental group students reported considerably elevated post-test motivation compared to the control group after baseline adjustment. Subscale analysis indicated that the greatest gains were concentrated in the Interest and Enjoyment dimension and the Perceived Competence dimension, findings that are directly consistent with self-determination theory's account of how game-based environments satisfy learners' fundamental psychological needs. Knowledge retention, measured by the Natural Science Knowledge Test, likewise significantly favoured the experimental group, with a large and meaningful effect size confirmed through covariance analysis.

Thematic analysis of interview data produced four recurring themes: enhanced enjoyment and anticipation of game-integrated sessions; deeper, action-grounded understanding of course content; improved peer collaboration and communication skills; and increased academic self-efficacy and professional confidence as future educators. Notably, multiple participants described the didactic games as professional models, expressing greater confidence in their ability to design and facilitate similar interactive activities in their own future classrooms - an unanticipated but practically significant finding with direct implications for teacher preparation.

The results provide robust empirical support for the effectiveness of didactic games in activating students' learning activity across cognitive, motivational, and knowledge dimensions. The very large effect sizes obtained ($d = 2.02$ to 2.78) indicate that the intervention produced not only statistically detectable but practically meaningful changes - a distinction of particular importance for educators and policymakers evaluating the cost-benefit calculus of methodological innovation. These findings extend prior meta-analytic evidence (Mayer, 2019; Boyle et al., 2016) to a Central Asian higher education context, demonstrating that the documented benefits of game-based learning generalise across educational systems with distinct socio-cultural and institutional characteristics.

The cognitive activation outcomes are well accounted for by constructivist theory: games require students to actively manipulate, classify, and apply knowledge within structured interactive scenarios, stimulating the elaborative, semantic processing associated with superior encoding and retention (Craik & Lockhart, 1972). The motivational findings align precisely with self-determination theory predictions: games satisfy autonomy needs through decision-making agency, competence needs through calibrated challenge structures, and relatedness needs through cooperative game formats. The qualitative emergence of professional identity development as a salient theme - not explicitly predicted by existing theory - suggests that didactic games may function as a form of legitimate peripheral participation in professional practice, allowing pre-service teachers to inhabit the role of interactive educator before formally assuming it. Several limitations must be acknowledged.

CONCLUSION

For educational practice, this study recommends that pedagogical universities invest in structured professional development programmes enabling instructors to design and facilitate learning-objective-aligned didactic games. Institutional timetables and physical learning environments should be adapted to accommodate interactive game-based sequences. The quasi-experimental design, while methodologically appropriate, precludes strong causal inference. The study is situated at a single institution, limiting immediate generalisability. Long-term retention effects beyond the immediate post-test were not measured, and the predominantly female sample composition may moderate the generalisability of motivational findings. Future research should employ randomised designs where feasible, include delayed retention assessments, and examine gender and cultural variables as potential moderators of game-based learning effectiveness.

For future research, cross-institutional studies within Central Asia, delayed retention assessments, and investigations of specific game-type effectiveness across diverse learning objectives are recommended. The present study contributes to the growing body of evidence positioning didactic games not as a peripheral enhancement but as a transformative pedagogical strategy capable of fundamentally reshaping the quality of student learning in higher education.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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2026. №4(1)

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.